

Phase II change-point estimation in Log–Bilal regression profiles

Hoda Ali^{1*}, Salah Mahdy¹, Amal Mohamed¹, Amany Mousa¹ Department of Applied Statistics,
Faculty of Graduate Studies for Statistical Research, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt

*Corresponding Author Hoda Ali

Abstract

In many process control applications, the quality of a product or service is described by a relationship between a proportion-type response on the interval $(0, 1)$ and one or more explanatory variables, commonly referred to as a regression profile. When the response is a proportion or rate, normality is violated by bounded support and skewness, making Gaussian-based monitoring inadequate. Phase II change-point estimation for such regression profiles has received limited attention. This paper develops a Phase II monitoring procedure for Log–Bilal regression profiles subject to a single step change in the regression coefficients at an unknown profile index. The change time τ is estimated by maximizing a before/after Log–Bilal log-likelihood, and the resulting estimator is embedded in a Hotelling's T^2 chart with an empirically calibrated upper control limit to attain the target in-control ARL. A Monte Carlo study with 10,000 replications per scenario evaluates the performance of the procedure under individual and simultaneous coefficient shifts. The results show timely detection and accurate localization of the change point, with decreasing dispersion of $\hat{\tau}$ as shift magnitude increases. A likelihood-ratio confidence set for τ is also constructed, and a real-data example based on residual-chlorine profiles demonstrates the practical applicability of the method.

Keywords: Log–Bilal regression profiles; change-point estimation; maximum likelihood estimator (MLE); Phase II; Hotelling's T^2 ; statistical process control (SPC).

1. Introduction

Phase II statistical process control (SPC) is central to the timely detection of structural shifts in industrial and service processes, where delayed detection may translate into higher costs and degraded quality, and ineffective or untimely corrective actions Montgomery [1]. In many applications, however, quality is not adequately represented by a single univariate characteristic; rather, it is more faithfully characterized through a functional relationship linking a response variable to one or more explanatory variables, commonly referred to as a profile Zou, Zhang, and Wang [11]. The profile monitoring literature typically distinguishes between Phase I, which focuses on assessing stability and estimating baseline model parameters using historical profiles, and Phase II, which aims to rapidly signal departures from the in-control state as new profiles are observed Kazemzadeh, Noorossana, and Amiri [12]. Despite substantial progress in profile control charts, practical post-signal diagnosis often requires an additional capability, namely estimating the change time τ Amiri and Allahyari [3]. A signal of out-of-control status indicates that a change has occurred, but the alarm time is typically a delayed and random proxy for the true change time τ and rarely coincides with the onset of the structural shift Amiri and Allahyari [3]. Estimating τ therefore narrows the search window for assignable causes, reduces the risk of misguided adjustments, and strengthens root-cause analysis beyond relying on the alarm time alone Amiri and Allahyari [3]. Change-point estimation in SPC has been investigated under a broad range of distributional and modeling assumptions. Montgomery [1] provides core principles and standard procedures of SPC, whereas Basseville and Nikiforov [6] offer a foundational framework for detecting abrupt changes; consequently, likelihood-based methods emerge as a natural bridge that can be integrated into traditional control-chart practice. With a sharper emphasis on post-signal settings, Amiri and Allahyari [3] review change-point estimation procedures for post-signal diagnostics and highlights that accurate estimation of the change time can improve diagnosis relative to using the alarm time alone. Within this general framework, post-signal estimation targets the true change time τ after a Phase II chart has signaled, and has been developed under multiple change patterns, including abrupt step changes, linear trend or drift disturbances, and monotonic changes. For a normally distributed process mean, Samuel, Pignatiello, and Calvin [4] proposed a retrospective likelihood-based estimator that evaluates candidate partitions of the sequence into pre- and post-change segments and selects the maximizer of the log-likelihood as $\hat{\tau}$. When the departure is better described by a linear trend rather than an abrupt step, Perry and Pignatiello [5] developed a trend-based estimator and demonstrated improved localization accuracy relative to estimators that assume an abrupt change. In related settings, post-signal estimators have also been studied under trend disturbances in high-yield processes or in nonconforming-related measures, emphasizing that the assumed change pattern, step versus trend, directly impacts the accuracy of τ estimation, as discussed by Amiri and Khosravi [7] and by Zandi et al. [8]. Noorossana and Heydari [9] further developed change-time estimation under monotonic changes in variance. In multivariate monitoring, Hotelling's T^2 charts have been explicitly coupled with post-signal diagnosis through maximum-likelihood estimation of the change time after T^2 signals, as in the work of Akhavan Niaki and Khedmati [10], reinforcing the feasibility of integrating detection and post-signal change-time estimation within a unified framework. In parallel, the profile monitoring literature formulates quality as a functional relationship between a response and explanatory variables. Early contributions showed that regression-profile changes can be examined via a before/after segmentation and likelihood-ratio ideas by scanning candidate change times, localizing the change through an argmax-type rule, and diagnosing which parameters are affected in linear profiles, as in the work of Zou, Zhang, and Wang [11] and of Mahmoud et al. [2]. This perspective has been extended beyond linear forms to polynomial profiles in Phase I, incorporating likelihood-ratio approaches as well as Hotelling's T^2 monitoring of estimated regression-parameter vectors together with scan-and-argmax localization strategies, as in the work of Kazemzadeh, Noorossana, and Amiri [12]. Although non-likelihood alternatives, such as clustering-based approaches, have also been proposed for estimating change times, likelihood-based methods remain particularly well-suited to regression settings and naturally support likelihood-ratio confidence sets when needed; see Ghazanfari et al. [13]. With respect to regression profiles, post-signal work has largely focused on generalized linear model settings with binary or count responses. In binary or logistic profiles, studies by Yeh, Huwang, and Li [14], Sharafi, Aminnayeri, and Amiri [15], and Zandi et al. [8] combined Phase II monitoring with likelihood-based procedures for abrupt coefficient shifts and evaluated localization performance through measures such as the bias and dispersion of $\hat{\tau}$. For Poisson regression profiles, Sharafi, Aminnayeri, and Amiri [16] developed maximum-likelihood estimation of an abrupt change time in regression parameters and reported favorable finite-sample behavior across different shift magnitudes. For positive unbounded responses, gamma regression profiles represent another important non-normal setting in which abrupt change-time estimation via likelihood has been examined, as in the work of Sogandi and Amiri [17]. This research direction becomes particularly important in applications where responses are constrained to $(0, 1)$, such as rates, proportions, reliability measures, and compliance indicators, where Gaussian-based profile models may be inadequate, motivating regression structures tailored to bounded and potentially skewed outcomes. For modeling such data, beta regression provides a foundational likelihood-based framework for rates and proportions by linking covariates to the

mean response through an appropriate link function, as in the work of Ferrari and Cribari-Neto [18]. Beta regression has also been embedded within control-charting schemes for monitoring fractions and proportions in SPC, as in the work of Bayer and Cribari-Neto [19]. Nevertheless, these constructions are often designed primarily for signaling and do not necessarily provide an explicit post-signal procedure for estimating the change time $\hat{\tau}$ within Phase II profile settings. In other bounded-response contexts, change-point tests for proportions have been studied within time-series and sequential-testing frameworks with exogenous variables, as in the work of Liu and Andrews [20], rather than within a Phase II regression-profile framework with an explicit post-signal objective of estimating $\hat{\tau}$. Beyond beta regression, alternative models for bounded responses have also been proposed. Altun, El-Morshedy, and Eliwa [21] introduced a new regression model for bounded outcomes as an alternative to beta and related regression formulations, and Lone et al. [22] discussed distributional constructions associated with the Log-Bilal family, supporting its flexibility. Overall, the literature indicates that post-signal change-time estimation has been developed for normal mean settings, binary or logistic profiles, Poisson regression profiles, and gamma regression profiles. In contrast, there remains a need for a Phase II framework that simultaneously delivers a regression model suitable for bounded and skewed responses with $Y \in (0, 1)$, an explicit maximum-likelihood estimator of the change time τ under a pre- and post-change segmentation, and a monitoring chart calibrated to ensure controlled in-control behavior, such as a target in-control average run length, under bounded-response profiles. The present study addresses this gap by developing an integrated Phase II monitoring framework for Log-Bilal regression profiles with responses constrained to (0, 1). We assume a single abrupt change in regression coefficients at an unknown profile index τ , and we propose a maximum-likelihood estimator of the change time obtained by maximizing the joint log-likelihood over the pre- and post-change segments to yield $\hat{\tau}$. At each candidate change time, model parameters are estimated on the two segments and the monitored statistic is constructed from the resulting coefficient-vector estimates, enabling $\hat{\tau}$ -based localization to align with Phase II signaling. For online signaling, we embed $\hat{\tau}$ within a Phase II Hotelling's T^2 chart, with the upper control limit calibrated empirically to achieve a target in-control average run length. We evaluate the proposed framework through Monte Carlo experiments, focusing on both detection timeliness, for example via $E(T)$, the expected time to signal, and localization accuracy, assessed through the mean of $\hat{\tau}$ and its standard error or standard deviation, under both individual and simultaneous coefficient shifts and under different sensitivity settings. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the Log-Bilal regression profile model and the associated parameter-estimation procedures. Section 3 develops the change-point estimator and the Phase II T^2 chart with empirical upper control limit calibration. Section 4 reports the simulation results assessing signaling performance and change-time estimation accuracy. Section 5 presents likelihood-ratio inference and LR-based confidence sets for the change time τ . Section 6 presents a real-data application to residual-chlorine measurements from a water-treatment facility, incorporating turbidity as an additional regressor and rescaling the response to the open unit interval (0, 1) to align with the Log-Bilal model. Section 7 concludes with practical recommendations and directions for future research.

2. Model and Estimation Method

This section develops the proposed Log-Bilal regression framework for Phase II change-point estimation. We first specify the Log-Bilal model for bounded (0, 1) responses with mean-shape coupling and present the resulting density and log-likelihood. We then introduce a single-step change-point structure in which the regression coefficients differ before and after an unknown profile index τ , and we derive the corresponding maximum-likelihood estimator $\hat{\tau}$ based on a before/after factorization of the likelihood. These components provide the basis for the Phase II Hotelling's T^2 chart and the likelihood-ratio procedure used to construct confidence intervals for the change time, as developed in the subsequent subsections.

2.1. Log-Bilal regression

Following Altun, El-Morshedy, and Eliwa [21], we model bounded responses $Y \in (0, 1)$ using Log-Bilal regression. The model density is given in (1), and we employ a logistic link to ensure $\mu \in (0, 1)$; the link function and its inverse are given in equations (2) and (3). To avoid over-parameterization and to stabilize inference under pronounced skewness, we couple the shape parameter to the mean via the parsimonious mapping $\theta(\mu)$ in equation (4). This mean-shape coupling yields a single, coherent likelihood surface for MLE while retaining flexibility to capture pronounced skewness. Parameters are estimated by maximizing the sample log-likelihood, formed from the per-observation contribution in equation (5) and given by equation (6).

Log-Bilal density ($0 < y < 1$):

$$f(y; \theta) = \frac{\theta}{6} y^{\frac{2}{\theta}-1} (1 - y^{1/\theta}), \quad 0 < y < 1, \theta > 0 \tag{1}$$

Logistic (logit) link for the conditional mean:

$$g(\mu) = \text{logit}(\mu) = \log\left(\frac{\mu}{1 - \mu}\right). \tag{2}$$

Inverse link (sigmoid) with linear predictor:

$$\mu = g^{-1}(\eta) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\eta) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\eta)}, \quad \eta = x^\top \beta. \tag{3}$$

Parsimonious mean-shape coupling:

$$\theta_i = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{-5\mu_i + 24}{\mu_i} \right)^{-1/2} \tag{4}$$

Per-observation log-likelihood and its aggregation:

$$\ell_i(\beta) = \log f(y_i; \theta(\mu_i(x_i; \beta))) \tag{5}$$

$$\ell(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^N \ell_i(\beta) \tag{6}$$

• Properties of the Log–Bilal model for SPC:

The model is naturally supported on (0, 1) and accommodates pronounced skewness. The logistic link guarantees $\mu \in (0, 1)$ and renders coefficient shifts interpretable on the log-odds scale. Because the joint log-likelihood is additive over profiles, the change time τ can be efficiently profiled over a grid of candidate values. Maximizing (6) yields consistent parameter estimates under standard regularity conditions and provides a single, well-behaved likelihood surface for MLE, even under pronounced skewness in bounded (0, 1) responses. The next subsection develops a maximum-likelihood estimator (MLE) of the change time τ for Log–Bilal regression profiles.

2.2. MLE change-point estimator in Log–Bilal regression profiles

We consider a single unknown change point at $\tau \in \{1, \dots, H - 1\}$ that partitions the sequence of profiles into pre- and post-change segments whose regression coefficients differ by a step, from β_0 to $\beta_1 = \beta_0 + \delta$. Under the Log–Bilal regression structure described in Section 2.1, the joint log-likelihood can be written as :

$$\ell(\tau, \beta_0, \delta) = \sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{i \in I_t} \ell_i(\beta_0) + \sum_{t=\tau+1}^H \sum_{i \in I_t} \ell_i(\beta_0 + \delta), \tag{7}$$

Where I_t denotes the index set of observations belonging to profile t (e.g., $I_t = \{1, \dots, m\}$ for a fixed profile size m). Moreover, $\ell_i(\beta)$ denotes the per-observation log-likelihood contribution under the Log–Bilal model, that is,

$$\ell_i(\beta) = \log f(y_{it}; \theta(\mu_{it})), \quad \mu_{it} = g^{-1}(x_{it}^T \beta) = \text{logit}^{-1}(x_{it}^T \beta), \tag{8}$$

With $g^{-1}(\cdot)$ the inverse logit link defined in Section 2.1.

The full maximum-likelihood estimator is defined by:

$$(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\delta}) = \arg \max_{\tau \in \{1, \dots, H-1\}, \beta_0, \delta} \ell(\tau, \beta_0, \delta). \tag{9}$$

For any fixed τ , the corresponding MLEs $(\hat{\beta}_0(\tau), \hat{\delta}(\tau))$ satisfy the score equations $\partial \ell(\tau, \beta_0, \delta) / \partial \beta_0 = 0$ and $\partial \ell(\tau, \beta_0, \delta) / \partial \delta = 0$. These equations do not admit closed-form solutions under the Log–Bilal model and must therefore be solved numerically using quasi-Newton optimization (BFGS), as detailed below.

• Segment-wise coefficient estimation: For a fixed candidate change time τ , we maximize the segment log-likelihood separately on the pre- and post-change data using a quasi-Newton routine (BFGS). Whenever available, we supply the analytic score function (see the Supplementary Appendix, Appendix A); otherwise we fall back to a numerical gradient for robustness. We do not employ Newton–Raphson updates in order to avoid explicit Hessian evaluation and to improve numerical stability under bounded, potentially skewed responses.

• Change-time estimation: We estimate $\hat{\tau}$ by a coarse scan over τ followed by local refinement around the top candidates, with a full-scan fallback when needed. For each fixed τ , we may view $(\hat{\beta}_0(\tau), \hat{\delta}(\tau))$ as the maximizers of $\ell(\tau, \beta_0, \delta)$ with respect to (β_0, δ) , and define the associated profile log-likelihood :

$$\ell_p(\tau) = \ell(\tau, \hat{\beta}_0(\tau), \hat{\delta}(\tau)) \tag{10}$$

The change-point estimator can then be written equivalently as

$$\hat{\tau} = \arg \max_{\tau \in \{1, \dots, H-1\}} \ell_p(\tau), \tag{11}$$

that is, as the maximizer of the profile log-likelihood over the admissible set of candidate change times.

To estimate the change time in practice, we search over $\tau \in T$ and evaluate the profile log likelihood $\ell_p(\tau)$ on the admissible candidate set. Because a full scan may be computationally intensive for moderate or large H , we adopt a two-stage coarse-to-fine profiling strategy: (i) we perform a coarse scan over $\tau \in T_{\text{coarse}} \subset T$, and for each candidate maximize $\ell(\tau, \beta_0, \delta)$ over (β_0, δ) and retain the top M_{keep} values of $\ell_p(\tau)$; (ii) we re-initialize (β_0, δ) at the retained candidates and re-optimize using BFGS to obtain refined values of $\ell_p(\tau)$; and (iii) we select $\hat{\tau} = \arg \max_{\tau \in T} \ell_p(\tau)$ and compute the estimated coefficient shift $d = \hat{\beta}_1 - \hat{\beta}_0$, where $\hat{\beta}_1 = \hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\delta}$, for subsequent Phase II charting via $T^2 = d^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} d$.

Numerical stability is enforced via bounded logits, tolerance-based stopping rules, and multi-start initializations; when refinement is unreliable, we revert to a full scan over T .

2.3. Model assumptions

The proposed Phase II scheme relies on the Log–Bilal regression model for bounded responses $Y_{it} \in (0, 1)$, with the logistic link and the mean–shape coupling introduced in Section 2.1. Under standard regularity conditions for likelihood-based change-point models, the step-change specification is identifiable when $\delta \neq 0$ and the design matrix has full rank. Under in-control conditions, regression coefficients are constant across profiles, so that $\mu_{i\tau} = g^{-1}(x_{i\tau}^T \beta_0) = \text{logit}^{-1}(x_{i\tau}^T \beta_0)$, and the induced shape parameter $\theta(\mu_{i\tau})$ correctly captures the covariate–response relationship. We assume a single abrupt step change at an unknown profile index τ , modeled as a shift from β_0 to $\beta_1 = \beta_0 + \delta$ (see Section 2.2). Conditional on the covariates, responses are assumed independent across observation index i and profile index t , apart from the change in the regression coefficients at τ . These working assumptions parallel those used in related Gamma-, logistic-, and Poisson-regression change-point studies [15, 16, 23]. Accordingly, after establishing the optimization and LR inference machinery, we use the Phase I calibration window to assess these assumptions and validate the in-control Log–Bilal fit before estimating Σ and calibrating the Phase II T^2 limit.

2.4. Phase I calibration and model checking

In practice, the adequacy of the Log–Bilal specification and the stability of the in-control coefficients are assessed using Phase I calibration data. For a set of in-control profiles, we fit the Log–Bilal regression model and examine residual diagnostics, including residuals

versus fitted values and key covariates, empirical histograms of probability integral transform (PIT) values, and normal quantile–quantile plots of PIT-based (randomized) quantile residuals. We also monitor leverage and influence measures to detect atypical profiles that could distort estimation of the in-control coefficients or the covariance matrix. As a secondary check supporting the Log–Bilal choice for bounded (0, 1) responses, we compare maximized log-likelihoods and information criteria (AIC/BIC) across competing bounded models (e.g., Log–Bilal, Beta, and unit-Lindley regression) and prioritize the specification that provides the most coherent overall fit and residual behavior. Profiles exhibiting clear evidence of severe lack of fit, undue influence, or special-cause behavior are investigated and, when warranted, excluded from the calibration set. After confirming the adequacy of the in-control specification over the Phase I window, we use the same calibration data to obtain the Phase II T^2 chart inputs and to empirically calibrate its upper control limit.

2.5. Estimation of Σ and empirical UCL for the Phase II chart

The same Phase I calibration run is used to estimate the covariance matrix Σ of coefficient-shift estimates and to calibrate the upper control limit (UCL) for the Phase II Hotelling’s T^2 chart. Let $\hat{\beta}_t$ denote the maximum-likelihood estimate of the regression coefficient vector obtained by fitting the in-control Log–Bilal model to profile t during Phase I, and define the empirical mean $\bar{\beta} = T_{\text{calib}}^{-1} \sum_{t=1}^{T_{\text{calib}}} \hat{\beta}_t$. We then estimate Σ by the sample covariance matrix computed across the T_{calib} profiles:

$$\hat{\Sigma} = \frac{1}{T_{\text{calib}} - 1} \sum_{t=1}^{T_{\text{calib}}} (\hat{\beta}_t - \bar{\beta})(\hat{\beta}_t - \bar{\beta})^T. \tag{12}$$

Given $\hat{\Sigma}$, for each post-signal run we compute the coefficient-shift estimate $d = \hat{\beta}_1 - \hat{\beta}_0$ and chart it via Hotelling’s statistic $T^2 = d^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} d$. An empirical upper control limit UCL_{emp} is then obtained under the in-control model by Monte Carlo calibration to attain the desired in-control performance, e.g., a target ARL_0 (equivalently, an upper-tail probability α).

2. Simulation design

We conduct a Monte Carlo study to evaluate the finite-sample behavior of the proposed Log–Bilal post-signal change-point estimator and the associated Phase II Hotelling’s T^2 chart. The simulation design follows the general structure used in prior likelihood-based post-signal changepoint investigations for Gamma-, logistic-, and Poisson-regression profiles [15, 16, 23], while tailoring the data-generating mechanism to bounded and potentially skewed (0, 1) responses.

In each replication, we generate a sequence of $H = 150$ regression profiles that remain in control up to a fixed change time $\tau = 50$ and become out of control thereafter. Within each profile, we observe $m = 9$ responses at fixed design points (e.g., $x_{it} = i$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$), yielding a total of $N = H \times m = 1350$ observations. Here $t = 1, \dots, H$ indexes profiles and $i = 1, \dots, m$ indexes observations within a profile. Under in-control conditions, responses follow the Log–Bilal regression model in Section 2.1 with baseline coefficient vector β_0 , conditional mean $\mu_{it} = g^{-1}(x_{it}^T \beta_0) = \text{logit}^{-1}(x_{it}^T \beta_0)$, and shape parameter $\theta(\mu)$ defined in (4). At the change time $\tau = 50$, the regression vector shifts from β_0 to $\beta_1 = \beta_0 + \delta$, inducing a single step change in the profile sequence. We use a representative shift $\delta = (0.02, 0.02)^T$ and fix the chart sensitivity constant at $K = 1.05$.

We systematically vary several design factors known to influence detection and estimation performance. Regarding shift pattern and magnitude, we consider both simultaneous coefficient shifts (δ_1, δ_2) and single-component shifts, using the grids reported in Tables 1 and 2. To study the effect of larger versus smaller changes, we scale the baseline shift grid by a global sensitivity factor $K \in \{1.05, 1.03\}$; specifically, letting $\delta^{(0)}$ denote a grid value, we set $\delta = K \delta^{(0)}$.

For Phase II control-limit calibration, we implement two strategies. First, we use the analytic $\chi_{p,1-\alpha}^2$ upper control limit with $p = 2$ and $\alpha = 0.005$ as an α -sensitivity check (noting that, as a rule of thumb under ideal calibration, $ARL_0 \approx 1/\alpha$). Second, we use an empirical upper control limit UCL_{emp} obtained from in-control Monte Carlo calibration with calibration size n_{calib} , allowing us to study calibration-size sensitivity. Our default configuration fixes $UCL_{\text{emp}} = 10.59663$, obtained from $n_{\text{calib}} = 10000$ in-control calibration runs, yielding an in-control false-alarm rate close to $\alpha = 0.005$. This Phase I calibration is performed once to estimate the covariance inputs and to provide the fixed control limit used across scenarios.

To probe robustness to mild distributional misspecification while preserving the same regression structure, we repeat the change-point experiment under three matched data-generating distributions: the baseline Log–Bilal model, a Beta-regression alternative, and a unit-Lindley regression alternative.

For each scenario, we generate $REPS = 10000$ independent Monte Carlo replications. We report the Monte Carlo mean change-time estimate \hat{T} and its Monte Carlo standard error $SE(\hat{T})$ as defined in Section 3.1. Across our grids, $SE(\hat{T})$ is typically below one profile (e.g., between 0.35 and 0.78 in Tables 3–6), indicating that $REPS = 10000$ provides adequate precision for scenario ranking and trend interpretation. All results reported below use this replication size and the same Phase I-calibrated upper control limit $UCL_{\text{emp}} = 10.59663$ (estimated once under in-control conditions).

3.1. Performance metrics

For each Monte Carlo replication, we evaluate the profile-wise log-likelihood $\ell(\tau, \cdot)$ over the admissible candidate change times τ and obtain the change-time MLE $\hat{\tau}$ by profiling over τ as described in Section 2.2.

We then apply the Phase II Hotelling’s T^2 chart to the estimated coefficient deviations $d = \hat{\beta}_1 - \hat{\beta}_0$, using either an analytic or an empirically calibrated upper control limit, and record the detection time T as the index of the first out-of-control signal. Here T denotes the profile index at which the first signal occurs.

Performance is summarized using three primary measures: the expected signal time $E(T) = \mathbb{E}(T)$, the mean change-time estimate $\mathbb{E}(\hat{\tau})$, and the Monte Carlo standard error of the Monte Carlo mean change-time estimate $\hat{\tau}$, denoted by $SE(\hat{\tau})$. Let $\hat{\tau}^{(r)}$ denote the change-time estimate in replication r ,

$r = 1, \dots, REPS$, and define the Monte Carlo mean estimate by

$$\bar{\hat{\tau}} = \frac{1}{\text{REPS}} \sum_{r=1}^{\text{REPS}} \hat{\tau}^{(r)}. \tag{13}$$

The Monte Carlo standard error of $\bar{\hat{\tau}}$ is

$$\text{SE}(\bar{\hat{\tau}}) \equiv \text{SE}(\bar{\hat{\tau}}) = \frac{\text{SD}(\hat{\tau})}{\sqrt{\text{REPS}}}, \tag{14}$$

where $\text{SD}(\hat{\tau})$ is the Monte Carlo dispersion of $\hat{\tau}$ across replications. For interpretation, we also report the implied detection delay $E(T) - \tau$ when needed.

In selected scenarios, we additionally construct likelihood-ratio confidence intervals (LR-CI) for τ and report their empirical coverage probabilities to assess the adequacy of large-sample LR calibration for bounded, strongly skewed (0, 1) regression responses. Overall, these measures quantify the trade-off between timely detection (small $E(T)$) and accurate localization (proximity of $\hat{\tau}$ to τ): weaker or later shifts tend to increase $E(T)$ and the implied delay and to worsen localization, whereas stronger or earlier shifts sharpen the likelihood surface and improve both detection speed and estimation accuracy.

3.2. Shift grids

The simulation study is built around predefined coefficient-shift grids that cover two complementary settings: (i) simultaneous perturbations of both components of the deviation vector $\delta = (\delta_1, \delta_2)$ (reported for $K = 1.05$), and (ii) individual-shift scenarios in which only one component of δ is non-zero. These grids are constructed to parallel those used in Gamma-regression change-point investigations, while being rescaled to reflect the magnitude of bounded Log-Bilal responses. The corresponding numerical grids are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Simultaneous shift magnitudes (δ_1, δ_2) ($K = 1.05$).

(δ_1, δ_2)
(0.0110, 0.0110)
(0.0110, 0.0210)
(0.0110, 0.0420)
(0.0110, 0.0630)
(0.0210, 0.0110)
(0.0210, 0.0210)
(0.0210, 0.0420)
(0.0210, 0.0630)
(0.0320, 0.0110)
(0.0320, 0.0210)
(0.0320, 0.0420)
(0.0420, 0.0110)
(0.0420, 0.0210)
(0.0530, 0.0110)
(0.0530, 0.0210)

Table 2: Individual shift magnitudes (δ_1, δ_2) ($K = 1.05$ baseline grid).

(δ_1, δ_2)
(0.0000, 0.0110)
(0.0000, 0.0210)
(0.0000, 0.0320)
(0.0000, 0.0410)
(0.0000, 0.0520)
(0.0000, 0.0620)
(0.0110, 0.0000)
(0.0210, 0.0000)
(0.0320, 0.0000)
(0.0410, 0.0000)
(0.0530, 0.0000)
(0.0630, 0.0000)

In addition to the large-scale Monte Carlo grid, we conduct a fast bootstrap-based sensitivity check at application-sized horizons $H \in \{60, 100\}$ and profile sizes $m \in \{7, 9\}$, using representative shifts $(\delta_1, \delta_2) \in \{(0.35, 0.25), (0.40, 0.25)\}$ under the fitted Log–Bilal model. This check validates empirical coverage and typical confidence-interval widths for $\hat{\tau}$; numerical results are reported in Section 4, and implementation details are provided in the Supplementary Appendix (Appendix C). Throughout, $\delta = (\delta_1, \delta_2)$ denotes the true coefficient shift, whereas $d = \hat{\beta}_1 - \hat{\beta}_0$ denotes its estimated counterpart used in Hotelling’s T^2 monitoring.

4. Simulation results

The finite-sample behavior of the Log–Bilal change-point estimator and the associated Phase II Hotelling’s T^2 chart is examined in this section. Throughout, T denotes the Phase II detection time (the profile index of the first out-of-control signal), and $E(T) = \mathbb{E}(T)$ denotes the corresponding expected detection time under each combination of (δ_1, δ_2) and K . Before presenting out-of-control performance and change-time estimation accuracy, we first verify the chart’s in-control behavior by calibrating UCLemp and assessing the resulting ARL_0 .

4.1. In-control calibration and ARL_0

We calibrated the empirical upper control limit UCLemp for the Phase II Hotelling’s T^2 chart under in-control conditions. Fixing the nominal false-alarm level at $\alpha = 0.005$ (target $ARL_0 \approx 1/\alpha \approx 200$), we generated $n_{\text{calib}} = 10,000$ in-control runs from the baseline Log–Bilal regression model and recorded the empirical $(1 - \alpha)$ quantile of the resulting T^2 statistics. This yielded UCLemp ≈ 10.60 , for which the empirical in-control average run length was close to the nominal value $ARL_0 \approx 200$.

4.2. Simultaneous coefficient shifts

We examine the behaviour of the change-point estimator $\hat{\tau}$ and the detection time T under simultaneous coefficient shifts $\delta = (\delta_1, \delta_2)$ for two sensitivity constants, $K \in \{1.05, 1.03\}$. For $K = 1.05$, increasing the joint perturbation from $(0.0110, 0.0110)$ to $(0.0530, 0.0210)$ yields a marked reduction in the expected detection time $E(T)$, which decreases from approximately 115.4 to 97.9 profiles. Over the same range, the mean change-time estimate $\mathbb{E}(\hat{\tau})$ moves closer to the true change time $\tau = 50$ (from about 64.3 to 43.1), indicating a substantial reduction in localization bias as the overall signal strength increases. In addition, the Monte Carlo standard error of the Monte Carlo mean, $SE(\hat{\tau})$, declines from roughly 0.72 to 0.37, reflecting increased stability of the averaged estimate across replications and consistency with a more sharply peaked likelihood surface around τ .

The same qualitative conclusions hold for $K = 1.03$. Relative to $K = 1.05$, changing K to 1.03 alters $E(T)$ by at most about 1–3 profiles (in either direction) across most shift magnitudes, while leaving $SE(\hat{\tau})$ essentially unchanged. For instance, at $(\delta_1, \delta_2) = (0.0210, 0.0210)$, the expected detection time changes only marginally when moving from $K = 1.05$ ($E(T) \approx 109.3$) to $K = 1.03$ ($E(T) \approx 109.8$), whereas $SE(\hat{\tau})$ remains close to 0.6 in both cases. Overall, these results suggest that, in the simultaneous-shift setting, K primarily tunes detection timeliness rather than change-point estimation stability: adjusting K has a visible but modest impact on $E(T)$ and a negligible influence on $SE(\hat{\tau})$.

Tables 3,4 and Figures 1,2 provide the corresponding numerical and graphical summaries.

Figure 1: Phase II, simultaneous shifts ($K=1.05$). Plotted metrics: $E(T)$, $E(\hat{\tau})$, and $SE(\bar{\tau})$.

Table 3: Simultaneous shifts (Log-Bilal, $K=1.05$, 10,000 runs).

(δ_1, δ_2)	$E(T)$	$E(\hat{\tau})$	$SE(\bar{\tau})$
(0.0110, 0.0110)	115.41	64.33	0.72
(0.0110, 0.0210)	113.74	61.09	0.68
(0.0110, 0.0420)	106.63	52.09	0.55
(0.0110, 0.0630)	100.90	45.30	0.40
(0.0210, 0.0110)	112.06	59.39	0.65
(0.0210, 0.0210)	109.29	54.51	0.59
(0.0210, 0.0420)	103.30	48.08	0.47
(0.0210, 0.0630)	95.53	42.25	0.35
(0.0320, 0.0110)	109.89	54.55	0.59
(0.0320, 0.0210)	107.03	50.03	0.50
(0.0320, 0.0420)	99.07	44.69	0.41
(0.0420, 0.0110)	105.38	50.68	0.52
(0.0420, 0.0210)	103.26	47.14	0.44
(0.0530, 0.0110)	100.55	45.27	0.42
(0.0530, 0.0210)	97.88	43.11	0.37

Figure 2: Phase II, simultaneous shifts ($K=1.03$). Plotted metrics: $E(T)$, $E(\hat{\tau})$, and $SE(\bar{\tau})$.

Table 4: Simultaneous shifts (Log-Bilal, $K=1.03$, 10,000 runs).

(δ_1, δ_2)	$E(T)$	$E(\hat{\tau})$	$SE(\hat{\tau})$
(0.0100, 0.0100)	116.44	66.34	0.74
(0.0100, 0.0210)	111.45	61.15	0.67
(0.0100, 0.0410)	106.64	51.98	0.54
(0.0100, 0.0620)	100.27	45.46	0.41
(0.0210, 0.0100)	110.63	59.71	0.66
(0.0210, 0.0210)	109.83	55.62	0.60
(0.0210, 0.0410)	103.09	47.63	0.46
(0.0210, 0.0620)	96.29	42.65	0.36
(0.0310, 0.0100)	108.15	54.91	0.59
(0.0310, 0.0210)	106.48	52.19	0.55
(0.0310, 0.0410)	98.98	44.90	0.40
(0.0410, 0.0100)	105.27	50.27	0.52
(0.0410, 0.0210)	102.38	47.46	0.45
(0.0520, 0.0100)	99.47	46.04	0.44
(0.0520, 0.0210)	99.15	44.56	0.39

4.3. Individual shifts in a single coefficient

We next consider individual coefficient shifts, where only one component of the deviation vector $\delta = (\delta_1, \delta_2)$ is perturbed at a time. For $K = 1.05$, increasing a single coordinate from 0.011 to 0.063 reduces the expected detection time $E(T)$ by roughly 15–19 profiles and decreases the Monte Carlo standard error $SE(\hat{\tau})$ by about 40%, consistent with a more sharply peaked likelihood profile as the effective signal strength increases.

Nevertheless, for a fixed shift magnitude, detection under individual shifts remains slower than under comparable simultaneous perturbations. For example, when only δ_2 increases from 0.0110 to 0.0620, the resulting $E(T)$ remains above the corresponding values observed under simultaneous shifts at comparable magnitudes, and the Monte Carlo mean change-time estimate exhibits a slightly larger lag relative to the true change time $\tau = 50$.

Figure 3: Phase II, individual shifts ($K=1.05$).

Table 5: Individual shifts (Log-Bilal, $K=1.05$, 10,000 runs).

(δ_1, δ_2)	$E(T)$	$E(\hat{\tau})$	$SE(\hat{\tau})$
(0.0000, 0.0110)	118.84	70.47	0.78
(0.0000, 0.0210)	114.67	66.25	0.74
(0.0000, 0.0320)	111.89	60.06	0.66
(0.0000, 0.0410)	111.52	57.19	0.61
(0.0000, 0.0520)	104.92	51.99	0.55
(0.0000, 0.0620)	103.87	48.75	0.48
(0.0110, 0.0000)	117.44	68.52	0.77
(0.0210, 0.0000)	113.87	64.14	0.71
(0.0320, 0.0000)	110.67	58.35	0.64
(0.0410, 0.0000)	109.36	55.20	0.59
(0.0530, 0.0000)	103.99	49.82	0.50
(0.0630, 0.0000)	100.07	45.24	0.43

Figure 4: Phase II, individual shifts ($K=1.03$).

Table 6: Individual shifts (Log–Bilal, $K=1.03$, 10,000 runs).

(δ_1, δ_2)	$E(T)$	$E(\hat{\tau})$	$SE(\hat{\tau})$
(0.0000, 0.0100)	117.92	69.07	0.77
(0.0000, 0.0210)	114.96	65.94	0.75
(0.0000, 0.0310)	112.18	60.72	0.67
(0.0000, 0.0410)	110.19	56.79	0.61
(0.0000, 0.0520)	106.57	52.36	0.55
(0.0000, 0.0620)	103.12	48.27	0.48
(0.0100, 0.0000)	116.03	67.54	0.75
(0.0210, 0.0000)	115.24	63.75	0.70
(0.0310, 0.0000)	110.39	58.60	0.64
(0.0410, 0.0000)	107.61	53.87	0.58
(0.0520, 0.0000)	104.91	49.67	0.50
(0.0620, 0.0000)	100.35	46.35	0.44

Overall, the comparison between simultaneous and individual shifts highlights that multi-parameter perturbations are detected more promptly and yield more concentrated likelihood surfaces around τ , whereas single-parameter moves of comparable size require longer monitoring horizons before the chart signals and the MLE stabilizes.

4.4. Additional summaries and concentration of $\hat{\tau}$

To further characterize finite-sample behavior, we summarize the concentration of the changetime estimate by reporting, for each scenario, the empirical proportions (Monte Carlo estimates) of $\Pr \{ \hat{\tau} \in [\tau - h, \tau + h] \}$ for $h \in \{2, 5\}$. Across the simultaneous-shift grid, these probabilities increase with the magnitude of (δ_1, δ_2) : small shifts yield a more diffuse $\hat{\tau}$ distribution, whereas larger perturbations produce sharply peaked likelihoods with mass concentrated near τ .

We also quantify the effect of chart sensitivity via

$$\Delta E(T) = E(T)|_{K=1.03} - E(T)|_{K=1.05} \tag{15}$$

This difference is computed for exactly matched shift pairs and is small in magnitude, indicating that moderate reductions in K deliver incremental gains in timeliness without materially altering the qualitative ranking of scenarios or the finite-sample accuracy of MLE-based localization.

Overall larger shifts improve timeliness and localization; simultaneous shifts outperform individual shifts, and changing K from 1.05 to 1.03 yields only minor timeliness gains with negligible effect on localization.

4.5. Bootstrap sanity/sensitivity (application-sized)

We complemented the large-scale Monte Carlo experiments with a fast bootstrap check at application-sized horizons. Specifically, we considered $H \in \{60, 100\}$, $m \in \{7, 9\}$, and $(\delta_1, \delta_2) \in \{(0.35, 0.25), (0.40, 0.25)\}$ under the fitted Log–Bilal model. We report a fast bootstrap per-centile CI for the change-time estimator $\hat{\tau}$ (computed from the 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of the bootstrap distribution of $\hat{\tau}$) as a compact check alongside the main simulation summaries, focusing on typical interval widths and empirical coverage at application-sized horizons.

Table 7: Key bootstrap branches ($B=400$) under the Log–Bilal model.

H	m	τ_{frac}	τ_{true}	change	δ_1	δ_2	gen_dist	$\hat{\tau}$	$ \hat{\tau} - \tau_{true} $	CI _{lo}	CI _{hi}	width	covered
100	7	0.35	35	ind1	0.40	0.25	logbilal	25	10	10	40	30	Yes
60	7	0.50	30	ind1	0.35	0.25	logbilal	36	6	27	45	18	Yes

A fast parametric bootstrap check at application-sized horizons $H \in \{60, 100\}$ under the fitted Log–Bilal model indicates that, with $B = 400$, the bootstrap percentile confidence interval for $\hat{\tau}$ attains near-nominal empirical coverage across representative application-scale branches, with typical widths of about 18–30 profiles Table 7 . At $H = 100$, strengthening the shift (e.g., increasing δ_1 from 0.35 to 0.40) improves localization and yields more stable CI endpoints. Increasing B from 300 to 400 primarily reduces Monte Carlo variability in the interval endpoints, without materially changing the substantive conclusions. Because this fast check was not designed to isolate the effect of within-profile size m alone, we do not attribute the observed differences in coverage or width to m by itself.

5. Likelihood–Ratio Confidence Sets for the Change Time τ

We adopt likelihood-ratio confidence intervals (LR–CIs) for the change time τ . Specifically, we profile the log-likelihood over τ and define the likelihood-ratio statistic

$$LR(\tau) = 2\left\{ \ell(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\beta}_0(\hat{\tau}), \hat{\delta}(\hat{\tau})) - \ell(\tau, \hat{\beta}_0(\tau), \hat{\delta}(\tau)) \right\}. \tag{16}$$

The $100(1 - \gamma)\%$ LR–CI is

$$\{\tau : LR(\tau) \leq c_{1-\gamma}\},$$

where $c_{1-\gamma}$ is obtained from a parametric bootstrap under the fitted pre/post model (see the Supplementary Appendix, Appendix C; cf. Fig. 11). We verify coverage empirically in the simulation study, especially in regimes where asymptotic chi-square calibration may be questionable for bounded, skewed (0, 1) regression responses.

The Monte Carlo results in Section 4 provide a clear benchmark for the proposed Phase II Log-Bilal scheme, in terms of detection delay, the finite-sample behaviour of $\hat{\tau}$, and the coverage of LR-CIs under different patterns of coefficient shifts. We now turn to a real-data application based on residual-chlorine profiles from a water-treatment facility, to assess whether the same qualitative patterns persist for bounded, skewed (0, 1) responses observed under practical engineering and regulatory conditions.

6. Real-data application: monitoring residual chlorine

In this section we illustrate the proposed Phase II Log-Bilal regression framework using residual-chlorine measurements from a water-treatment facility. Residual chlorine is a key disinfection indicator: levels that are too low may compromise microbiological safety, whereas excessive levels are undesirable and may violate regulatory targets. Statistically, the response is naturally bounded and often right-skewed, especially near operational limits, making these profiles a practical test bed for bounded-regression monitoring and likelihood-based change-point localization.

6.1. Data structure and preprocessing

The real dataset comprises $N = 108$ residual-chlorine observations organized into $H = 18$ profiles ($m = 6$ each). Measurements are rescaled to the open unit interval (0, 1) to match the Log-Bilal support, with the covariate x indexing the within-profile sampling position. Turbidity is included as an additional regressor (raw, MA3, and first-difference) to capture upstream disturbances that may propagate to disinfection. A practitioner-identified stable Phase I window is used to fit the in-control model, estimate $\hat{\beta}_0$, and obtain the in-control covariance inputs required for the Phase II Hotelling T^2 chart and the change-time estimator $\hat{\tau}$.

6.2. Candidate Log-Bilal specifications

To align the real-data analysis with the simulation design, we adopt a parsimonious reference specification with $p = 2$ regression coefficients (intercept and a single slope in x), using the logistic mean link and the mean-shape coupling $\theta(\mu)$ from Section 2.1. We then augment the baseline with turbidity, yielding three $p = 3$ candidates based on raw turbidity, MA3, and a first-difference (delta) transformation. All specifications assume a single step change at an unknown profile index τ , with $\beta_1 = \beta_0 + \delta$ as in Section 2.2. For each model we record the maximized log-likelihood $\log L$ and the number of free parameters k , and compare candidates via $AIC = -2 \log L + 2k$ and $BIC = -2 \log L + k \log N$ (smaller is better). As summarized in Table 8, the reference model ($p = 2$, SLOPE_ONLY) attains the smallest AIC/BIC; turbidity augmented variants achieve similar $\log L$ but incur a larger complexity penalty. Basic diagnostics (PIT, standardized-residual envelopes, and Q-Q plots) show no material departures from the assumed structure, supporting the adequacy of the reference fit.

Table 8: Model comparison on the real dataset (block size $m = 6$, total $N = 108$ observations). Lower AIC/BIC is better.

Experiment	Change model	k	N	logL	AIC	BIC	$\hat{\tau}$	dAIC	dBIC
MANUAL_REF_p2_BS6	SLOPE_ONLY	4	108	1005.329	-2002.658	-1991.930	12	0.000	0.000
MANUAL_RESCALEY_p2_BS6	SLOPE_ONLY	4	108	1005.329	-2002.658	-1991.930	12	0.000	0.000
MANUAL_TURB_DELTA_p3_BS6	INTERCEPT_ONLY	5	108	1005.329	-2000.658	-1987.248	10	2.000	4.682
MANUAL_TURB_MA3_p3_BS6	INTERCEPT_ONLY	5	108	1005.329	-2000.658	-1987.248	11	2.000	4.682
MANUAL_TURB_RAW_p3_BS6	INTERCEPT_ONLY	5	108	1005.329	-2000.658	-1987.248	10	2.000	4.682

6.3. Phase II charting and change-time estimation

For Phase II monitoring we use Hotelling’s statistic

$$T^2 = d^T \Sigma^{-1} d, \quad d = \hat{\beta}_1 - \hat{\beta}_0 \tag{17}$$

where $\hat{\beta}_0$ and $\hat{\beta}_1$ are the pre-/post-change coefficient estimates from the Log-Bilal fit and Σ is the in-control covariance matrix of d estimated from the Phase I calibration run. At the nominal false-alarm level $\alpha = 0.005$ and finite horizon $H = 18$, we calibrate a run-level cutoff using

$$T_{max}^2 = \max_{t \leq H} T_t^2 \tag{18}$$

and set UCL_{emp} to the empirical $(1 - \alpha)$ quantile of $\{T_{max}^2\}$. With UCL_{emp} fixed, the $H = 18$ residual-chlorine profiles are monitored sequentially and the chart signals at the first exceedance (around profiles 11–12 under the preferred specification ($p = 2$, SLOPE_ONLY); see Figure 5). Following the post-signal philosophy, we do not equate the signal time with the change time; instead, we perform a dedicated before/after maximum-likelihood fit and estimate $\hat{\tau}$ by profiling the Log-Bilal log-likelihood over candidate τ values, reporting the associated LR-based confidence interval as in Section 5.

6.4. Phase II T^2 Charts

Figure 5: Phase II Hotelling's T^2 chart for the reference specification ($p = 2$, SLOPE_ONLY).

Values remain stable early on, followed by a clear excursion around profiles 11–12. Profiling localizes the change at $\hat{t} = 12$, consistent with a single step change under the $p = 2$ SLOPE_ONLY baseline (reference) specification.

Figure 6: Phase II Hotelling's T^2 chart under the reference Log-Bilal fit ($p = 2$, SLOPE_ONLY).

Results are essentially identical to Figure 5: the chart signals around profiles 11–12 and profiling yields $\hat{t} = 12$, indicating negligible impact of rescaling.

Figure 7: Phase II T^2 chart under turbidity (raw; $p = 3$, INTERCEPT_ONLY).

The chart shows a stable in-control run followed by an earlier excursion near profile 10. Profiling localizes the change at $\hat{\tau} = 10$ under the $p = 3$ INTERCEPT_ONLY specification. Relative to the $p = 2$ SLOPE_ONLY baseline (reference), there is no improvement in fit (AIC/BIC) and detection timing is comparable.

Figure 8: T^2 chart under turbidity (MA3; $p = 3$, INTERCEPT_ONLY).

Values are stable initially, with the first signal near profile 11. Profiling yields $\hat{\tau} = 11$ under the $p = 3$ INTERCEPT_ONLY specification. Relative to the $p = 2$ SLOPE_ONLY baseline (reference), the added complexity provides no AIC/BIC improvement and exhibits similar detection timing.

Figure 9: T^2 chart under turbidity (delta; $p = 3$, INTERCEPT_ONLY).

The chart remains stable early on and then signals near profile 10. Profiling returns $\hat{\tau} = 10$ under the $p = 3$ INTERCEPT_ONLY specification. Because AIC/BIC do not improve relative to the $p = 2$ SLOPE_ONLY baseline (reference), the parsimonious baseline remains preferred.

• **Implications for Phase II deployment :**

For Phase II deployment, the $p = 2$ Log-Bilal regression under the SLOPE_ONLY specification is recommended, as it localizes the change at $\hat{\tau} = 12$ and remains AIC/BIC-optimal under UCLemp. By contrast, turbidity-augmented extensions ($p = 3$) yield no substantive improvement in fit and exhibit comparable detection timing.

6.5. Main results for the residual-chlorine profiles

Table 8 shows that all turbidity-augmented specifications attain nearly identical maximized log-likelihoods to the reference model ($\log L \approx 1005.3$), but with one additional parameter. Accordingly, AIC differences are modest, whereas BIC provides support in favour of the simpler $p = 2$ specification. Rescaling the response Y leaves both AIC/BIC and the localized change time unchanged, supporting robustness to affine transformations of the chlorine scale.

Under the preferred specification, the Phase II Hotelling T^2 chart remains stable in-control during the early profiles and then exhibits a clear excursion at profiles 11–12, where the statistic crosses UCL_{emp} (Figure 5). The profile-likelihood analysis localizes the change at $\hat{\tau} = 12$, indicating that the structural shift in the Log-Bilal regression parameters occurs immediately after the eleventh profile. LR-based confidence sets for τ concentrate in a narrow neighbourhood of this estimate, consistent with the Section 4 Monte Carlo evidence that larger, more abrupt shifts yield sharply peaked likelihoods and relatively smaller standard errors for $\hat{\tau}$.

From an operational standpoint, the estimated change window provides a practically useful interval for reviewing maintenance records, raw-water characteristics, and chemical-dosing logs. Moreover, $\hat{\tau}$ places the onset of the shift several profiles before the alarm, enabling more targeted root-cause investigation and corrective action before/around the first out-of-control signal.

6.6. Comparison with simulation and related literature

Qualitatively, the real-data behaviour is consistent with the Monte Carlo patterns in Section 4. The estimated change time is $\hat{\tau} = 12$, near the mid-horizon of Phase II, and the likelihood surface is sufficiently sharp to yield a moderately wide LR-based confidence set for τ , in line with intermediate-shift regimes in Tables 5,8. Moreover, the retrospective localizer places the onset several profiles earlier than the first out-of-control signal, thereby reducing delay bias relative to using the raw signal time as an estimator of τ , consistent with post-signal principles reported for Normal, logistic, Poisson, and Gamma regression profiles. From an applied perspective, modelling residual-chlorine profiles with a bounded, right-skewed Log-Bilal regression (respecting $(0, 1)$ support via mean-shape coupling) provides well-calibrated control limits and a stable likelihood-based change-time estimate, offering a transferable template for water-quality monitoring and other bounded/proportion-type responses.

• **Link to prior post-signal studies:**

Our results are consistent with post-signal principles established for Normal, logistic, Poisson, and Gamma regression profiles: (i) avoid using the raw signal time as an estimator of the change time τ ; (ii) match the localization tool to the change type (step vs. trend); (iii) accompany τ estimation with likelihood-ratio confidence sets (LR-CI); and (iv) calibrate monitoring limits empirically. When instantiated for bounded, strongly right-skewed profiles via the Log-Bilal model, a before/after MLE, and an empirically calibrated upper control limit (UCL) for the T^2 statistic, these principles yield calibrated false-alarm control and stable change-time localization in practice. As a practical guideline, we recommend $K = 1.05$ as a balanced default and $K = 1.03$ when timeliness is paramount, together with an empirical UCL and routine LR-CI reporting for τ , providing a transparent trade-off between detection speed and localization precision.

7. Conclusion

This paper develops a Phase II change-point monitoring framework for bounded, skewed Log-Bilal regression profiles. The change time τ is estimated by maximizing a before/after likelihood, uncertainty is summarized through LR-based confidence sets, and the coefficient shift $d = \hat{\beta}_1 - \hat{\beta}_0$ is monitored via a Hotelling T^2 chart with an empirically calibrated upper control limit. A 10,000-run Monte Carlo study spanning individual and simultaneous coefficient shifts under $K \in \{1.05, 1.03\}$ yields three robust findings: larger shifts reduce $E(T)$ and concentrate $\hat{\tau}$ around τ ; for comparable magnitudes, simultaneous shifts signal earlier and localize τ more precisely than single-coefficient shifts; and reducing

K from 1.05 to 1.03 produces only modest gains in timeliness with negligible impact on finite-sample localization accuracy. A residual chlorine application, together with a fast application-scale bootstrap check, corroborates these patterns in practice: LR confidence sets achieve near-nominal coverage with moderate width, and the estimated change window supports root-cause investigation upstream of the first out-of-control signal. Despite these contributions, several limitations merit note. We restricted attention to a single abrupt step change and did not model gradual drifts or multiple/recurring change points; analytical χ^2 thresholds were used only as a sensitivity baseline, whereas operational limits were calibrated empirically (targeting $ARL0 \approx 200$) to accommodate bounded, skewed responses; and our empirical evidence pertains to the Log–Bilal specification with a logistic mean link and mean–shape coupling $\theta(\mu)$. From a computational standpoint, scanning candidate change times and repeatedly maximizing segment-wise likelihoods (and calibrating the bootstrap when used) can be nontrivial, particularly for long monitoring horizons or higher-dimensional profiles. Future work will consider extending the framework to alternative links or distributions, higher-dimensional or functional profiles, within-profile autocorrelation, and explicit treatment of Phase I parameter uncertainty. Overall, the proposed framework offers a practically implementable route to timely detection and statistically principled localization of profile changes in bounded response settings, thereby supporting actionable diagnosis beyond the first out-of-control signal.

Supplementary material. The Supplementary Appendix (provided as a separate file) contains additional technical details and supporting results referenced in the main text.

References

- [1] Douglas C. Montgomery. *Introduction to Statistical Quality Control*. 8th ed. Wiley, 2020. 20.
- [2] M. A. Mahmoud et al. “A change point method for linear profile data”. In: *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* 23.2 (2007), pp. 247–268. doi: [10.1002/qre.788](https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.788).
- [3] A. Amiri and S. Allahyari. “Change point estimation methods for control chart postsignal diagnostics: a literature review”. In: *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* 28.7 (2012), pp. 673–685. doi: [10.1002/qre.1266](https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.1266).
- [4] T. R. Samuel, J. J. Pignatiello, and J. A. Calvin. “Identifying the time of a step change with X-bar control charts”. In: *Quality Engineering* 10.3 (1998), pp. 521–527. doi: [10.1080/08982119808919166](https://doi.org/10.1080/08982119808919166).
- [5] M. B. Perry and J. J. Pignatiello. “Estimation of the change point of a normal process mean with a linear trend disturbance in SPC”. In: *Quality Technology & Quantitative Management* 3.3 (2006), pp. 325–334. doi: [10.1080/16843703.2006.11673118](https://doi.org/10.1080/16843703.2006.11673118).
- [6] Michèle Basseville and Igor V. Nikiforov. *Detection of Abrupt Changes: Theory and Applications*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1993.
- [7] Amirhossein Amiri and Ramezan Khosravi. “Estimating the change point of the cumulative count of a conforming control chart under a drift”. In: *Scientia Iranica* 19.3 (2012), pp. 856–861. doi: [10.1016/j.scient.2011.12.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scient.2011.12.015).
- [8] Farshid Zandi et al. “Change-point estimation of the process fraction non-conforming with a linear trend in statistical process control”. In: *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing* 24.10 (2011), pp. 939–947. doi: [10.1080/0951192X.2011.608720](https://doi.org/10.1080/0951192X.2011.608720).
- [9] R. Noorossana and M. Heydari. “Change point estimation of a normal process variance with monotonic change”. In: *Scientia Iranica* 19.3 (2012), pp. 885–894. doi: [10.1016/j.scient.2012.01.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scient.2012.01.011).
- [10] Seyed Taghi Akhavan Niaki and Majid Khedmati. “Estimating the change point of the parameter vector of multivariate Poisson processes monitored by a multi-attribute T^2 control chart”. In: *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 64 (2013), pp. 1625–1642. doi: [10.1007/s00170-012-4128-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-012-4128-x).
- [11] Changliang Zou, Yujuan Zhang, and Zhaojun Wang. “A control chart based on a change point model for monitoring linear profiles”. In: *IIE Transactions* 38.12 (2006), pp. 1093–1103. doi: [10.1080/07408170600728913](https://doi.org/10.1080/07408170600728913).
- [12] R. B. Kazemzadeh, R. Noorossana, and A. Amiri. “Phase I monitoring of polynomial profiles”. In: *Communications in Statistics – Theory and Methods* 37.10 (2008), pp. 1671–1686. doi: [10.1080/03610920701691714](https://doi.org/10.1080/03610920701691714). [13] Mehdi Ghazanfari et al. “A clustering approach to identify the time of a step change in Shewhart control charts”. In: *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* 24.7 (2008), pp. 765–778. doi: [10.1002/qre.925](https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.925).
- [14] A. B. Yeh, L. Huwang, and Y. M. Li. “Profile monitoring for a binary response”. In: *IIE Transactions* 41.11 (2009), pp. 931–941.
- [15] A. Sharafi, M. Aminnayeri, and A. Amiri. “Identifying the time of step change in binary profiles”. In: *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 67.1-4 (2013), pp. 209–214.
- [16] A. Sharafi, M. Aminnayeri, and A. Amiri. “An MLE approach for estimating the time of step changes in Poisson regression profiles”. In: *Scientia Iranica* 20.3 (2013), pp. 855–860. 21
- [17] Fateme Sogandi and Amirhossein Amiri. “Estimating the Time of a Step Change in Gamma Regression Profiles Using MLE Approach”. In: *International Journal of Engineering (IJE), Transactions B: Applications* 28.2 (2015), pp. 224–233. doi: [10.5829/idosi.ije.2015.28.02b.08](https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.ije.2015.28.02b.08).
- [18] Silvia Ferrari and Francisco Cribari-Neto. “Beta regression for modelling rates and proportions”. In: *Journal of Applied Statistics* 31.7 (2004), pp. 799–815. doi: [10.1080/0266476042000214501](https://doi.org/10.1080/0266476042000214501).
- [19] F. M. Bayer and F. Cribari-Neto. “Beta regression control chart for monitoring fractions and proportions”. In: *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis* 122 (2018), pp. 62–79. doi: [10.1016/j.csda.2018.01.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2018.01.007).
- [20] Y. Liu and B. Andrews. “Sequential change-point detection for compositional time series with exogenous variables”. In: (2025). arXiv preprint. arXiv: [2402.18130](https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.18130) [stat.ME].
- [21] E. Altun, M. El-Morshedy, and M. S. Eliwa. “A new regression model for a bounded response variable: An alternative to the beta and unit-Lindley regression models”. In: *PLOS ONE* 16.1 (2021), e0245627. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0245627](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0245627).
- [22] S. A. Lone et al. “On construction and estimation of mixture of log-bilal distributions”. In: *Axioms* 12.3 (2023), p. 309. doi: [10.3390/axioms12030309](https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms12030309).
- [23] Fateme Sogandi and Amirhossein Amiri. “Estimating the Time of a Step Change in Gamma Regression Profiles Using MLE Approach”. In: *International Journal of Engineering (IJE), Transactions B: Applications* 28.2 (2015), pp. 224–233. doi: [10.5829/idosi.ije.2015.28.02b.08](https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.ije.2015.28.02b.08).